

Deliverable 6.4

Revised Dissemination and Exploitation Plan, with Toolkit and Resources

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Abstract (for public dissemination only)	<p>This document provides detail of the instruments, tools and processes to be deployed by the Games Realising Effective Affective Transformation (GREAT) project partners and associates to engage stakeholders, raise awareness and leverage the project outcomes, outputs, findings and results. In conjunction with the supporting, associated, dynamic ‘activity plan’ the document will be used by the project to inform, manage and operationalise dissemination and exploitation activities. The core elements of the plan are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● To provide an integrated and consistent external profile for the project, to facilitate recognition, raise awareness and engage identified target groups. ● To ensure visibility of the project’s actions, activities, outcomes, research findings, and events. ● To disseminate extensively and intensively the achievements of the project and the effectiveness of the GREAT approach to targeted audiences. ● To leverage the international networks that are linked to consortium members. ● To provide a roadmap for successful commercial and non-commercial exploitation of the project outcomes. <p>This is the revised version of the deliverable (D6.2) which has been updated and revised with a second iteration at a later point of the project in month 30. This updated version (D6.4) has incorporated specific details of activities undertaken, strategic updates and reflections informed by the emergent experience of the project as it progressed.</p>
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List of Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Confidential
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DI	Digital Innovation
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EB	Editorial Board
EC	European Commission
EGE	The European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulations
GREAT	Games Realising Effective Affective Transformation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KER	Key Exploitable Result
UKRI	United Kingdom Research & Innovation
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

The EU Horizon Europe GREAT project (Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation) presents an opportunity to provide new insight and understanding of the cultural and social potential of digital games. It will achieve this through undertaking research inquiry to provide and pilot innovative solutions that harness the agency and scale of gaming audiences to generate valuable insight into society with the aim of creating a step change in citizens' participation in public debate. Moreover, it offers unprecedented opportunities to exploit the scale, speed, agility and diversity of inquiry and in the collection of data. The project will engage with three core aspects; games, data and policy in a single programme of research and innovation with the ambition of applying games to create a new form of engagement and dialogue between citizens and policy stakeholders (policy makers, policy implementers, political parties, campaigning organisations and affected citizens). In doing so, the project aims to demonstrate that digital games have the potential for positive impact on social engagement, by harnessing the innovative potential of a game space within which citizens are willing to express their preferences and attitudes.

The purpose of this deliverable, in conjunction with D6.5 Sustainability Strategy, is to provide strategic direction to raise awareness of the project and its intended outputs, engage key stakeholders and gather input, and the exploitation and sustainability of the intended outputs. The document will contribute to the longevity of the project outputs, discussing scalability and repeatability through a playbook toolkit accessible from the project website. The project will engage positively with industry to ensure a rich project legacy of outputs, outcomes and methodologies. The focus of the WP6 is to “*reach and engage stakeholder groups to input expertise and perspectives into the project, share findings, outputs and recommendations and inspire maximum uptake from stakeholder groups, and beyond.*” and the core elements of this deliverable within it are to:

- provide an integrated and consistent external profile for the project, to facilitate recognition, raise awareness and engage identified target groups.
- ensure visibility of the project's actions, activities, outcomes, research findings, and events.
- disseminate extensively and intensively the achievements of the project and the effectiveness of the GREAT approach to targeted audiences.
- leverage the international networks that are linked to consortium members.
- provide a roadmap for successful commercial and non-commercial exploitation of the project outcomes.

The primary audience for this deliverable is internal, the Executive Management Board (EMB) of the GREAT project; to inform the EMB of the rationale behind the recommendations to deploy appropriate tools and instruments to engage stakeholders. This deliverable and specifically the associated activity plan will enable the partners of the project to identify, manage and undertake dedicated dissemination activities consistent with the project aims and objectives. The associated activity plan will function as a dynamic repository of dissemination and exploitation activities for the duration of the project.

As part of the updated dissemination and exploitation strategy, a new Games for Impact Toolkit has been developed, is available [here](#) and a small description is included in Appendix 1. This digital resource provides practical, accessible guidance for game developers and partners on how to embed climate action and sustainability themes within game design and communication. The toolkit supports the project's objective of empowering wider sectoral engagement and serves as a replicable asset to extend the project's legacy beyond its duration.

2. Introduction

The GREAT project is committed to maximizing its impact by actively disseminating and exploiting its findings from the outset. Since February 2023, we have engaged with diverse stakeholders, including policymakers, games companies, and the general public, through targeted activities guided by evidence-based, data-driven processes. This commitment extends to collaboration with associated Horizon Europe innovation projects and initiatives. This document outlines our comprehensive approach to *communication*, *dissemination*, and *exploitation*, ensuring the project's methodology, data, and technology are leveraged effectively. This second iteration of Deliverable D6.4 reflects valuable insights gained from stakeholder engagement throughout the project and provides clear guidance for leveraging project outcomes. The following presents three Key Focus Areas:

1. **Communication:** Informing the general public about the project and its outputs through various channels, including press releases and social media. We leverage the reach of existing games to connect with a diverse audience, ensuring balanced representation across gender, age, education level, and location. For example, Play2Act has a global and diverse demographic reach, demonstrating our ability to engage with a wide range of individuals from different countries, social, economic and educational background, age etc. This is explained in detail in section 3.
2. **Dissemination:** Sharing results with specific target groups using tailored messaging and audience segmentation strategies. This approach (detailed in Table 1 and explained in detail in section 4) ensures strong connections and effective knowledge transfer. Activities include:
 - Presenting at international conferences, workshops, and webinars.
 - Publishing in academic journals, scholarly texts, and industry periodicals.
 - Depositing academic outputs in the Zenodo EU repository.
 - Producing white papers and guidance documents for policy stakeholders.
3. **Exploitation:** Putting the project's results into practice. This includes:
 - Developing a user-friendly GREAT toolkit with practical guides for applying the project's methodology.

- Providing long-term access to anonymized data on Climate Policy Radar.
- Maintaining a project website (<https://www.greatproject.gg> with regular blog posts and updates).

This multifaceted approach ensures that the GREAT project's valuable contributions reach a wide audience and are effectively utilized to address critical societal challenges. This is explained in detail in section 5.

3. Communication Strategy and Plan

Communication is how we inform the general public of the project, and this can be through press releases, media and other more general ways to reach a wider audience. This is important because citizens play a huge role in the overall project and are a key stakeholder, as the methodology and data should have a direct benefit to global citizens. As part of the communications strategy, the project has an advantage to reach vast and diverse audiences through existing games. Games have a variety of audiences depending on the genre, platform and type of model (free vs premium) which is all tracked in the data and enable the project team to keep a close eye on diversity of the audience and results.

The goal, or mission of the internal communications strategy is to have a clear plan for partners to follow, to communicate and disseminate information, either to the wider public or specific stakeholder groups. The process will enable PlanetPlay to be the central source to manage communications, but give each partner the flexibility to raise awareness of the activities that may be specific to them. Although this WP is led by PlanetPlay, each partner is responsible for contributing to the work package as a variety of documents, from blogs to scientific papers, are created to raise awareness and engage stakeholders through dissemination to exploit the results in a variety of ways. Each project partner will create and communicate different outputs, attend events, or make a discovery. For each of these items, each partner is responsible for following the workflow below:

1. **ALL:** In the bi-weekly meeting, each partner discussed dissemination activities that they have been involved in.
2. **ALL:** If there is nothing to report, please state this. Partners will be expected to contribute to dissemination at least every 8 weeks, ideally monthly.
3. **ALL:** Create a short blog about the dissemination activity (event attended, speaking slot, paper, discovery etc.) with text and visuals, and bullet points to summarise the activity or the action, and send to PlanetPlay to be uploaded onto the project website.
4. **PP:** Post the blog onto the website first, then post blog on LinkedIn (to drive more traffic to the website overall) with hashtags #greatprojectgg and other associated hashtags such as #play2act (hashtags will enable a quick search and filter to review engagement results).

5. **PP:** Share posts by email to ALL partners and ALL partners expected to share on their LinkedIn profiles, for their organisations and individually (collective reach of 500k followers across profiles on LinkedIn).
6. **ALL:** On a monthly basis, PlanetPlay will review the collective data and add to a tracker to keep a track of engagement metrics.

PlanetPlay will generate a suite of assets which can be edited by each partner such as social post templates, academic posters etc.

4. Dissemination Strategy, Plan and KPIs

There are multiple target groups identified through audience segmentation (the first iteration of our segmentation strategy is provided in Table 1) that the project will actively engage with during the duration of the project. Our audience segmentation strategy will be refined as the project evolves. At the centre of the project dissemination will be the dynamic activity document. This will be subject to ongoing review by the project team to regulate and monitor the efficacy of all communication and dissemination activities to ensure that the project strategy is refined and remodelled logically and incrementally to reflect stakeholder engagement input.

4.1 Methodology

The dissemination process objectives are to stimulate the interest and attention of the identified audiences and target groups. The messaging and ways in which we communicate through a range of channels, will be dynamically reviewed as we deliver messaging, to understand the efficacy of our communication approaches and strategy as well as the mechanisms and channels selected, which will be refined and adjusted by ongoing audience feedback. The dissemination process/cycle is detailed in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: Dissemination Methodology

4.2 Target Groups

To engage with stakeholders, we have identified various audiences and the communication methods, tools and instruments by which to engage them with.

Target Groups	Primary Messages	Communications Tool, Instruments and Channels
Citizens and game players	GREAT provides new ways for you to provide input and effect to policy makers and implementers, in a simple, convenient way.	Embedded activities in games giving broad reach to a variety of demographics across gender, age and education level. Press releases, blog posts on the website, social media.
Academia (games researchers, social scientists, technologists)	GREAT research provides new insights and evidence of the efficacy of digital games and their potential role in society.	Research publications, conferences, bibliographic listings on the GREAT website, journals, periodicals and books (consortium partners have published a number of books/journal articles/papers on relevant topics with major publishing houses.
a) Games publishers and providers b) Games developers	a) GREAT reveals new opportunities for new applications of games, with guidance, resources, demonstrators and business models. b) GREAT provides a method and resources to implement games. leveraging game data for social purposes.	Blog posts on the GREAT website. Industry conferences (e.g. Games for Change, GDC, Gamescom, Pocketgamer, SXSW). Social media. Networking by partners. Targeted contributions to industry websites (e.g. ISFE, EDPF) and leading bloggers. For data analytics: SOLAR, LACE network.
a) Policy makers b) Policy implementers c) Environmental policy stakeholders	a) The GREAT method offers new ways to consult with citizens who do not participate in the traditional media and democratic process, and to assess their preferences and attitudes (reaching the hard to reach) b) The GREAT method is a new way to obtain feedback on results of policy implementation c) GREAT insight reports can help you in formulating and responding to policy on the climate crisis	Networking by partners (e.g. with UNESCO, UNECE, House of Lords UK) and policy events (Institute of Government and Public Policy, User Centred Policy Design, (Apolitical), social media. Press releases and newsletters. Participation in climate crisis conferences (Davos, UNGA, COP, PlanetTech, Websummit, TedX, and UN, events run by UNEP, UNFCCC and UNDP). Hosting roundtables at the EU Commissions buildings in Brussels bringing together policy makers and games studios, policy makers attending events / roundtables at gaming events i.e. Nordic Game 2025.
Political parties, campaigning organisations	The GREAT method creates opportunities for widening participation in your activities.	Press releases, targeted distribution of newsletters and insight reports. Social media

Table 1: Audience Segmentation (Target Groups and Comms Channels).

The segmentation is not intended to be a prescriptive approach as with any iterative, agile project evolves, our expectation is that the segmentation and associated methods, tools and

instruments will evolve, new groups emerge as informed by our continuous stakeholder engagement.

4.3 Editorial Board

All project partners will contribute to the development of content and participate in dissemination activities. However, an Editorial Board (EB), which are the WP leaders, has been established to manage, advise, regulate and monitor the quality, relevance and adequacy of content and messages being communicated as directed and informed by this plan. The GREAT editorial Board will initially consist of the following members as representatives of the contributing partners to the project.:

DIPF Jane Yau
 ZSI Claudia Fabian
 PM Jude Ower
 UNIR Joaquin Alonso
 UoB Rebecca Harris
 SGI Simon Egenfeldt-Nielsen
 FU Anna Merry

It is envisaged that regular meetings of the EB will take place to collate, review and approve content and materials informed by the dynamic activity plan. The purpose of the board is to ensure that the project will maintain a dynamically rich and multichannel flow of information, material and content, from the expertise and perspectives of the partner organisations. Ongoing dissemination content and materials have been incorporated into the dissemination and exploitation plan provided in this deliverable.

Figure 2: EB Approval Structure

4.4 Deliverables and Milestones

Table 2 shows the related deliverables concerned with dissemination and exploitation of the GREAT project.

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Title	Type	Due Date	Comments
D6.1	Website	Website	07.2023	The website hosts project and partner information, updates, whitepapers and social media links. Access to games and data will be linked too.
D6.2	Dissemination and Exploitation Plan	Report	04.2023	Available at: https://zenodo.org/records/14622766
D6.3	Business Models	Report	07.2024	Available at: https://zenodo.org/records/14622491
D6.4	Revised Dissemination and Exploitation Plan, with Toolkit and Resources	Report	07.2025	This report will be deposited on Zenodo.
D6.5	Sustainability Strategy	Report	01.2026	This report will be deposited on Zenodo.

Table 2 Dissemination and Exploitation, as well as other Deliverables within WP6

4.5 Channels, Tools and Instruments

To facilitate effective communication with segmented audiences and maintain ongoing dialogue engagement with the project, the following channels tools and instruments are deployed by the project:

- The GREAT website contains project information, partner information, and updated, dynamic information including live data and materials including papers, games and tool kits. A guide has been developed for social and website posts.
- The Project will establish a mailing list on the website to include email registration subject to GDPR requirements.
- The EB will coordinate the updating of the website and develop a project e- newsletter to be distributed periodically during the duration of the project as required.
- Social media accounts will be established on Twitter, Bluesky and LinkedIn, the latter believed to be the most beneficial for the project. These will be updated regularly during the duration of the project and coordinated by the EB.
- Assets for social posts and logos including project and funders' logos will be used.
- Partner reports and papers will be produced by all partners and coordinated by the EB. These will be from a variety of perspectives on emergent topics within GREAT.
- Proactive public relations (PR) activities will also help to drive awareness and new followers/collaborators, and each partner will be asked to undertake PR activities as required. A Relations pack will be produced, which will also be available on the website, and can be shared by the whole project groups / partners (ALL).

- In-game activations will also drive awareness of the project, and engagement from the player community (engaged over one million gamers / citizens to date).
- The project established a Scientific Committee (located in WP4), which is responsible for the custodianship of all academic activities. This responsibility includes all academic dissemination. The Scientific Committee exercises oversight of ethics and quality control procedures in compliance with EU and UKRI requirements for the duration of the project.

4.6 Activities

The consortium will undertake a range of activities to raise awareness of and engage with the project key target audiences with a view to building relationships with relevant individuals and organisations. As highlighted earlier in this section, the dynamic activity plan is the repository and location of all dissemination and engagement activities and events and details of the project partners who are responsible (see Table 3), where the first column denotes whether it is a communication (c) or dissemination (d) activity. Note that completed events appear as blog posts at www.greatproject.gg/blog.

D / C	Starting	Ending	Channel	Target Audience	Dissemination	Activity Name	status	Lead
	1/2/23	30/06/23	Website	All	Other	Website	Ongoing	PM
C	23/3/23	23/3/23	Event	Industry, busine	Conferences	Speak at Sustainable Innovation 2023	Delivered	UoB
C	6/23	6/23	Event	Innovators	Conferences	Speaking at Irish Games Based Learning Conference (Cork)	Delivered	UoB
C	17/7/23	25/7/23	Event	Industry, busine	Conferences	Games for Change Festival	Delivered	PM
C	20/7/23	30/7/23	Event	Industry, busine	Conferences	SDG Summit at the UN/Raising profile via a book launch and ongoing book promotion	Delivered	PM
C	9/23	9/23	Event	Innovators	Conferences	European Games Based learning Conference (ECGBL) Netherlands	Delivered	UoB
C	9/23	9/23	Event	International org	Conferences	UN General Assembly	Delivered	PM
C	5/23	5/23	Event	Research comm	Conferences	Presentation at an International Conference	Delivered	UoB
C	5/23	5/23	Event	International org	Meetings	Presentation to UN working Group	Delivered	UoB
C	6/23	6/23	Event	International org	Conferences	Presentation at the International Conference of Young Scientists held in conjunction with the Global Young Academy Annual General Meeting	Delivered	DIPF
C	6/23	6/30	Event	Research comm	Conferences	Presentation of Irish Game-Based-Learning Conference	Delivered	SGI
C	7/23	7/23	Event	International org	Conferences	Presentation at a key side event of World Young Scientist Summit 2023 - Int. Young Scientists Forum on Ecology and Resource Sustainable Development of Silk Road	Cancelled	DIPF
C	7/23	7/23	Event	Research comm	Conferences	Plenary Presentation at the Young Scientist Network Academy of Sciences Malaysia	Delivered	DIPF
C	12/8	16/8	Event	Industry, busine	Conferences	Gamescom Cologne	Delivered	PM
C	9/23	9/23	Event	International org	Conferences	Presentation at the Brazilian-German Frontiers of Science and Technology Symposium "Climate Change and the Challenges to a Sustainable Development" in the Healthcare session	Delivered	DIPF

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C	10/23	10/23	Event	Research comm	Conferences	Presentation at the international conference of the APA Division 34 (Society for Environmental, Population and Conservation Psychology)	Delivered	ZSI
C	9/6	06/09/2023	Exhibition	All	Conferences	Stand with DiBL and climate game to attract interest and partners	Delivered	SGI
C	1.11.2023	3.11.2023	Event	Research comm	Conferences	Conference contribution	Delivered	SGI
C	30.10.2023	1.11.2023	Event	Research comm	Conferences	Project presentation at Virtual Conference "The impact of diversity on research quality: exploring the knowledge gap"	Delivered	DIPF
C	18.9.2023	18.9.2023	Event	EU Institutions	Collaboration wit	1st Meeting - GREAT Project presentation with sister projects	Delivered	DIPF
C	9.11.2023	9.11.2023	Event	EU Institutions	Clustering activi	2nd Meeting - EU sister projects - potential collaboration	Delivered	DIPF
C	8.1.2024	8.1.2024	Event	EU Institutions	Clustering activi	3rd - Meeting - EU sister projects - potential collaboration	Delivered	DIPF
C	2.2024	2.2024	Event	EU Institutions	Collaboration wit	4th Meeting - EU sister projects - potential collaboration	Delivered	DIPF
C	4.2024	4.2024	Event	EU Institutions	Collaboration wit	5th Meeting - EU sister projects - potential collaboration	Delivered	DIPF
C	5.2024	5.2024	Event	EU Institutions	Collaboration wit	6th Meeting - EU sister projects - potential collaboration	Delivered	DIPF
C	9.2024	9.2024	Event	EU Institutions	Collaboration wit	7th Meeting - EU sister projects - potential collaboration	Delivered	DIPF
C	11.2024	11.2024	Event	EU Institutions	Collaboration wit	8th Meeting - EU sister projects - potential collaboration	Delivered	DIPF
C	12.2024	12.2024	Event	EU Institutions	Collaboration wit	Meeting - EU sister projects - Nordic Game planning	Delivered	DIPF
C	2.2025	2.2025	Event	EU Institutions	Collaboration wit	Meeting - EU sister projects - Nordic Game planning	Delivered	DIPF
C	4.2025	4.2025	Event	EU Institutions	Collaboration wit	9th Meeting - EU sister projects - potential collaboration	Delivered	DIPF
C	6/23	6/23	Print mate	International orj	Other scientific c	Published magazine article "Technological innovations for advancing quality education, gender equality and climate action" in the Global Young Academy Connections Magazine (2023), pp.25-27. DOI: https://doi.org/10.26164/GYA_00799	Delivered	DIPF
C	18/11	20/11	Event	Industry, busine	Conferences	Speaking on a panel about games for good and talking about GREAT	Delivered	PM
			Interview	Citizens	Other	Climate Coalition EU - Channel for Climate Talks	Ongoing	DIPF
C	01/24		Video	All	Other	GREAT presentation video	Delivered	UNIR
C	2.24	2.24	Event	International orj	Other	Presentation at the UNESCO Institute for Lifelong Learning	Delivered	DIPF
C	3.24	3.24	Event	Industry, busine	Conferences	Games Developer Conferenece	Delivered	PM
D	3.4.24	6.4.24	Event	All	Conferences	European Citizen Science Conference	Delivered	ZSI
D	15.4.24	17.4.24	Event	Research comm	Conferences	World Forum for Women in Science	Delivered	DIPF
C	23/4/24	23/4/24	Event	Industry, busine	Meetings	Gaming x Climate Change Roundtable	Delivered	PM
D	5.24	5.24	Event	Research comm	Conferences	Int. Conf. of Young Scientists	Delivered	DIPF
D	5.6	5.6	Event	EU Institutions	Other	Online Round table for EU and member countries on future Cultural EU strategy	Delivered	SGI
D	6.24	6.24	Event	Research comm	Conferences	IEEE GEM 2024	Delivered	DIPF
D	6.24	6.24	Event	Research comm	Conferences	IEEE GEM 2024	Delivered	UoB
D	6.24	6.24	Event	Research comm	Conferences	IEEE GEM 2024	Delivered	UoB
D	6.24	6.24	Event	Industry, busine	Collaboration wit	Creative Business Panel Gaming within Cultural Heritage	Delivered	SGI
D	28.6.24	28.6.24	Event	Research comm	Conferences	Changing Cities Conference	Delivered	FU
D	8.24	8.24	Event	Industry, busine	Conferences	Dilemma-based Learning Games stand	Delivered	SGI
D	8.24	8.24	Event	Industry, busine	Conferences	Dilemma-based Learning Games talk	Delivered	SGI
D	10.24	10.24	Event	Research comm	Conferences	ECGBL	Delivered	UoB
D	28.9.24	28.9.24	Exhibition	Citizens	Education and tra	Eduotec @ Science Festival Frankfurt	Delivered	DIPF
D	28.10.24	1.11.24	Event	International orj	Conferences	Conference Presentation and proceedings - Eenviro Conference Bucarest	Delivered	FU
D	11.11.24	14.11.24	Event	Industry, busine	Conferences	Web Summit	Delivered	PM
C	29.11.24	29.11.24	Event	EU Institutions	Other scientific c	MSCA Green Charter Update meeting	Delivered	DIPF
D	1.25	1.25	Interview	Research comm	Other	DIPF Press Office	Delivered	DIPF
D	3.25	3.25	Media arti	Citizens	Other	partizipation.at	Delivered	ZSI
D	21.5.25	24.5.25	Event	Industry, busine	Conferences	Nordic Game & Games Policy Summit	Delivered	PP
D	2.10.25	2.10.25	Event	Research comm	Conferences	ECGBL	Ongoing	DIPF

Table 3: A complete list of dissemination and communication activities undertaken by GREAT

The activities to be included but are not limited to in the dynamic activity plan:

1. **Conferences**

The project will take part in targeted conferences, such as:

- i. Speaking opportunities i.e., the UN SDG & Gaming Summit
- ii. Hosting panels and roundtables
- iii. Hosting workshops or masterclasses
- iv. Distributing papers and data

2. **Associated Events**

When there are opportunities to engage with fringe events and activities, such as:

- i. Side presentations
- ii. Socials
- iii. Workshops/roundtables both virtual and physical representation

3. **Focus Groups**

GREAT will engage with focus groups online and offline to investigate specific topics or challenges. This activity may be undertaken alongside the project activities in citizen science located in WP5 of the GREAT project.

4. **Associated Existing Groups/Activities**

GREAT will engage with established and associated groups, activities and initiatives that may relate to the project, such as:

- i. Online forums and networks including ‘Playing for the Planet’,
- ii. GGJ, United Kingdom Interactive Entertainment (UKIE)
- iii. Sustainability Group, International Game Developers Association (IGDA)
- iv. Games Developers Association Special Interest Group (GDA/SIG), COP, UNDP People’s Climate Vote (other climate and policy event).

5. **Engagement with associated EU Funded Horizon Europe Projects**

The project has engaged with our associated sister projects commencing with a virtual meeting with the projects in May 2023 with the objective of introducing our project to consider which synergies, clustering activities would benefit our respective projects specifically in respect of the future dissemination of the results and the potential for collective preparation of policy recommendations. The five sister projects are:

- i. **EPIC-WE** (Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments)
- ii. **LoGaCulture** (Locative games for cultural heritage)
- iii. **i-Game** (Building a community for the co-creation of games with high impact on innovation, sustainability, social cohesion, and growth)

- iv. **MEMENTOES** (Immersive games for museums as vehicles to engage visitors in empathetic responses)
- iv. **MuseIT** (Multi-sensory, User-centred, Shared cultural experiences through interactive technologies)
- v. **GAME-ER** (Gaming Clusters across Multiple European Regions)
- vi. **Gamehearts** (Games, Heritage, Arts & Sport: the economic, social, and cultural value of the European videogame ecosystem)
- vii. **Hamlet** (Collaborative Community Hub, a digital platform where artists, designers, game developers and cultural professionals connect, communicate, share expertise and co-create)

4.6.1 Upcoming events in the last six months of the project (Aug 25 – Jan 26)

The last six months of the project is crucial for the dissemination and exploitation of the GREAT project results. The following activities are currently being planned to take place:

1. A roundtable event in Sep 2025 at the Danish Embassy together with UNDP staff in New York (location of the UN headquarters), where a larger number of game studios will be attending. The number of attendees will surpass that of the last roundtable event taken place in Sep 2024. The aim of the event is to increase the scale and impact of GREAT. A policy brief / whitepaper on the topic of games democracy education will be the outcome of this event, as well as the dissemination of the toolkit.
2. Two academic conference papers have been accepted at the European Conference on Games Based Learning, to be held in Norway from 1-3 October 2025, including a paper titled: “*The reach of digital games and their potential as global communication tools*” relating to the Play2Act1 case study, and one relating to the Waterwise case study, which will be presented at the conference with the dissemination of the project results.
3. Two journal papers have been accepted in the Journal of Computer Assisted Learning Special Issue – one relating to the UNDP Exploratory case study and the other relating to the Waterwise case study. Academic journal or conference papers are either published or planned covering each case study in the project.
4. GREAT consortium partners will be planning to attend a number of gaming or policy events such as Gamescon in August as well as the Web Summit in November (PP). One objective is also to share the Business Models report more widely with the public and these events would be suitable for this purpose too. SGI might be attending Online Educa in December and PP/UoB might be attending DAVOS in January 2026, if there is an opportunity to do so. The latter event will support the project to reach a larger number of policy-makers.
5. The planning of a final dissemination event is currently under discussion by the GREAT consortium. This will likely take place towards the end of January 2026 at the European Parliament in Brussels, where EU policy officers, game studios

and UNDP as well as other case studies representatives will be invited to attend. Additionally, we will explore the possibility of hosting this event with sister projects at the game cluster in order to increase collaboration potential. One main aim of the meeting will be to disseminate the project toolkit as well as its findings and to make further collaborations with various participants from different stakeholder groups to increase the scale and impact of the project results.

4.7 Dissemination Instruments and Tools

4.7.1 The Project Logo

The GREAT project has its own distinct logo, which will be used on all materials including the web site, publications, presentations, blog and social media posts. The logo is a vibrant visual which sums up gaming which is used in conjunction with a simple type font of GREAT.

Figure 3: The logo for the GREAT EU project.

4.7.2 Funders Logos

Consistent with the grant agreement alongside the GREAT logo, the EU Horizon Europe logo and UKRI logo will be applied across all materials as demonstrated in this footer of this document, this will be the standard document template for all deliverables. Material will also contain as required the project Grant Agreement Number and accompanying text.

“This [insert appropriate description, e.g. report, publication, conference, infrastructure, equipment, insert type of result, etc.] is part of the project / joint action ‘101094766 / GREAT’ which has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme (2023 - 2026)”

When displayed in association with another logo, the EU emblem will have appropriate prominence. For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries will use the EU emblem and accompanying caveat note.

“The content of this [insert appropriate description, e.g. report, publication, conference, etc.] represents the views of the author only and is his/her sole responsibility; it cannot be considered

to reflect the views of the European Commission and/or the Consumers, Health, Agriculture and Food Executive Agency or any other body of the European Union. The European Commission and the Agency do not accept any responsibility for use that may be made of the information it contains.”

Figure 4: Logos of the funding agencies of the GREAT project.

4.7.3 Presentations

The project team will be required to attend events and present materials. In this context, presentation decks will also be used to generate material, which are not reports or whitepapers. A template has been created for the project team. The Great Project Presentation Template document is also presented below:

Figure 5: GREAT Project Presentation Template.

4.7.4 Website

The website (<https://www.greatproject.gg>) is a key tool leveraged for dissemination, communication and exploitation. It will be a central hub which will host and/or link to various information and materials to raise awareness and provide detailed information of the project, and the progress and results, as the project develops. We will present the following:

- 1) Project overview and partners
- 2) Games (The DiBL - Dilemma Based Learning Games)

- 3) Reports, white papers and other publications
- 4) Data dashboard (link to GitHub or other such repository)
- 5) Methodology details
- 6) Social media links
- 7) PR and media (with approval for usage on the site or link to the site)
- 8) Project Playbook and Toolkit (when available)
- 9) Link to Zenodo
- 10) Policy documents

This list is not exhaustive and throughout the project we will accommodate other materials and outputs that emerge to present to stakeholders or the result of stakeholder consultation.

Figure 6: Website Landing Page.

Key dates for the website development are:

- 15th May - Landing page live.
- 30th June - Website launched.

The editorial board (EB) will meet periodically to discuss website content and agree materials and information as this is incorporated. Each member of the EB will have access to the website Content Management System to upload information and material. Quality control will be managed by the EB on an ongoing basis.

4.7.5 Hashtags

For all posts on social channels, mainly LinkedIn and X, the following hashtags will be used in order to enable the WP leader to track engagement data on posts and mentions:

- The main project hashtag = #greatprojectgg
- Case Studies can also be tagged, such as = #play2act

4.8 Progress on KPIs for Dissemination

There are several Key Performance Indicators (KPI) for dissemination activities incorporated into the Grant Agreement document, and this provides quantitative targets for the project. The EB will work across all work packages to ensure that these KPIs are achieved. Table 5 highlights the KPIs set out at the start of the project with an updated view on progress now in M30. All of the targets have either been completed (or are currently on track) by the GREAT consortium as a whole.

General Public (communication)	Games Industry (dissemination)	Policy Stakeholders (dissemination)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website (100,000 unique visitors) • Player communications (3 million contacts) • Open participation in games (300,000 players) • Participation in design of games and data analysis (100 per cycle) • Press releases (at least each 6 months) • Social media (at least monthly to Twitter) • Research publications (at least 20) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conference presentations (20, at least 5 at industry events or trade fairs) • Academic publications in games journals (5) • Social media (monthly to LinkedIn & Discord) • Participation in EC events (3, if suitable) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meetings with key stakeholders (25 formal meetings) • Insight briefings for policy makers (5) • Toolkit for games companies (1, updated) • GREAT described in magazine and external website articles (at least 6)

Table 4: Planned Activity KPIs of the GREAT project from the DoA

	Target by M36	Reached by M30
1.	20 Publications	(On track) 12 Publications published - Hollins et al. (2023a) , Hollins et al. (2023b) , Tlili et al. 2024 , Griffiths et al., 2024 , Iwendi et al., 2024 , Watson et al. 2024 , Yau et al., 2024 , Kieslinger et al. 2024 , Bunt et al., 2024 , Hollins et al., 2024 , Merry et al., 2024 , Merry et al., 2025 7 accepted - Iwendi et al. (2025) From play to policy: evaluating climate-focused digital games for environmental behaviour and governance. IEEE GEM. Iwendi et al. (2025) Levelling up for nature: Pathways of engagement with green messages in games. IEEE GEM. Iwendi et al. (2025) Gaming for the planet: Exploring belief, motivation and behaviour in climate-conscious play. IEEE GEM. Yau et al. (2025) The reach of digital games and their potential as global communication tools. ECGBL.

		<p>Watson et al. (2025) Reimagining water security education through playful engagement. JCAL Special Issue. Harris et al. (2025) Dialogue through play: Games as a bridge for citizen engagement. JCAL Special Issue. Watson et al. (2025) <i>Paper relating to the Waterwise case study</i>. ECGBL.</p> <p>1 upcoming poster presentation Kieslinger et al. (2025) <i>Poster relating to the Green Jobs case study</i>. Event in Austria.</p> <p>1 under review - Harris et al. (2025) Games without borders: Digital play as a global communicative infrastructure for climate policy engagement. Int. Journal of Games and Social Impact.</p> <p>In progress - Academic papers relating to the Play2Act2, Play2Act3, Prosper case studies.</p>
2.	3 Policy Insight Briefings (300 downloads)	(On track) 2 completed (1 - https://zenodo.org/records/12777953 - 213 downloads, and (2 - https://zenodo.org/records/14968119 & also whitepaper) - 158 downloads, in total 372 downloads), 1 more policy brief to be completed after the UN event in Sep 2025
3.	5 Case Study Reports	(Completed) 6 published on https://zenodo.org/communities/101094766
4.	Project Video (600 views)	(On track) Video produced in Jan 2024 (241 views) Another Video will be produced towards the end of the project (and expecting 350+ views)
5.	500 participants in co-design & activities	(Completed) 140 in Test Cycle & 200 in Green Jobs & 115 in Green Roofs. Planned participants for Play2Act Data workshops, Play2Act2, Cyprus, etc.
6.	300,000 players engaged	(Completed) 980,000 players engaged
7.	3 million players reached	(Completed) 130 million players reached across 20 games titles and platforms including Xbox, Unity and Amazon Games
8.	Engagement of diverse participants in > 8 countries	(Completed) 190 countries covered, Play2Act participants were ca. 50% male, 40% female, 10% non-binary/did not want to say. Play2Act2 and Play2Act 3 (as well as other current case studies – Waterwise and Cyprus) will be designed to increase the diversity of participants, as much as possible.
9.	Collaborative engagement with 25 rep. from games companies & policy bodies	(Completed) Currently 30 game studio partners, 3 games platforms and 7 policy bodies
10.	5 Industry Presentations	(Completed) 11 including Web Summit, SXSW, Games for Change, participated in Nordic Game in May 2025
11.	20 presentations at external conferences/events	(Completed) 26 presentations at external conferences/events
12.	50 mentions of Policy Insight Briefings in external climate websites	(On track, see Appendix 2) UNDP Play2Act Press Release and results have been mentioned by 23 external game studios and climate websites. (Upcoming) Waterwise organization (UK) has offered the use of their database platform for hosting a high-level public-facing summary of the GREAT project. This would include a general description of the aims, methodology, and conclusions, and would link to published academic papers & policy briefs.
13.	Stakeholders in workshops give positive evaluation	(Completed) Very positive feedback from industry, policymakers, gamers (NYC Climate Week roundtable with SYBO games & UNDP roundtable for Earth Week April 2024) Very positive feedback from participants and sister projects at the EU Brussels games clusters event on 17.6.25

14.	12 games (or approaches) to gather data which is valuable for policy stakeholders.	<p>(On track) Relating to the DiBL approach, we will deliver at least six fully designed games. With the PP approach, we will provide six examples of how its survey technology can be used within existing games to gather valuable data from players. As stated in D3.1, in total, we will cover 12 games that demonstrate in different ways how to gather valuable data for policy makers. These different methodologies will be documented and analysed in the case studies. The collected data will be made available for open access (as defined in section 4 of D3.1). At the time of writing, 4 DiBL games are available, as follows:</p> <p>Prosper DiBL: a cooperative policy-making simulation game about the UN's Sustainable Development Goals. This page contains all materials necessary to run this game. Prosper Link</p> <p>Green Jobs DiBL: A roleplaying exercise about getting young people interested in the developing sector of green jobs. This page contains all materials necessary to run this game. Green Jobs Link</p> <p>Green Rooftops DiBL: Playful policy-making and reflective roleplaying exercises about green utilization of rooftop spaces. This page contains all materials necessary to run this game. Green Roofs Link</p> <p>Waterwise DiBL: a facilitated learning game about water scarcity. This page contains all materials necessary to run this game. Waterwise Link</p> <p>Upcoming – UNDP Exploratory PP, Play2Act1 PP, Play2Act2 PP, Play2Act3 PP, Cyprus DiBL, Waterwise PP A game jam is planned together with EPIC-WE sister project where we will invite students to create games relating to water sustainability based on the Waterwise case study. A number of games are expected from this.</p>
15.	30 Policy Bodies taking steps to adopt GREAT methods	<p>(Completed) Currently 129, Austrian Climate Agency, Cyprus Energy Agency, Urban Gorillas, Waterwise, UNDP (collaborating with 120 governments around the world for the Climate Promise), House of Lords (UK), New Automotive, Dept of Environment in SA, European Commission, Cyprus Ministry of Education</p>
16.	Games industry give positive feedback	<p>(Completed) Very positive feedback on value, input on business model and roundtables (April and Sept 2024), games studios are talking about the GREAT project on stage at major conferences such as SXSW</p>
17.	1000 downloads of Business Models	<p>(On track) Currently this report has been downloaded 753 times. It was released on 31.7.2024.</p>
18.	A page of relevant work by other researchers	<p>(Completed) Zenodo community (Zenodo) & Zotero Group (Zotero)</p>
19.	Create a LinkedIn group	<p>(Completed) linkedin.com/groups/12833899/</p>
20.	5 Press releases (every 6 months)	<p>(Completed) currently 5 (Kick-off, Earth Week 2024, UNDP Play2Act 2024, Web Summit 24, UNDP Play2Act 2025) Upcoming ones will include the announcement by UNDP for the Play2Act2 and Play2Act3 launch and results dissemination, FU will release a press release relating to the Cyprus case study, for example.</p>
21.	6 magazines / websites refer to GREAT	<p>(Completed) 7 in the Global Young Academy (Connections Magazine, 2023, 2024), Falling Walls, UNDP, Mirage News, Devdiscourse, Digital Frontiers</p>
22.	10,000 followers across all GREAT social media activities	<p>(Completed) UNDP Play2Act press release (& other materials) out to gain broader public interest & followers. Also tracking collective following = 541k followers on LinkedIn and 85k followers on X (organisations and personal accounts). Partners also share on wider social channels such as Instagram, Facebook and Tiktok, such as games studios sharing their involvement and encouraging public participation. It has been decided that a more relevant KPI for this project is to track engagement with social posts from the consortium on communication and dissemination activities, is likes, shares and comments to posts across</p>

		Linkedin, Facebook, X and Instagram. Aiming for followers to the project felt a risk to losing the engagement of interested stakeholders when the project is complete. However engaging with posts and consortium members, has more longevity and is more meaningful to the project as a whole.
23.	1000 downloads / views of Newsletter	(On track) Currently counting 1100 website visitors. UNDP Play2Act press release (& other materials) have been published to gain wider public interest & viewers, and collaborations with major industry publications. As the project had intense work phases throughout, blogs were published on the GREAT website after each dissemination and communication event including the publishing and presentation of results in academic and industry conferences. The following newsletters have been produced which also included a short summary of recent GREAT events that have been listed in blog posts - Newsletter1 (summary of the first year of the project, 34 downloads) Newsletter2 (summary of month 12-18 of the project, 31 downloads) Newsletter3 (released in July 2025, 17 downloads) More time and effort will be spent to circulate the newsletters in the last 6 months of the project.
24.	A whitepaper on the use of games democracy education	(On track) This will be created from the roundtable event in New York with the UN and game studios, which will take place in September 2025.
26.	A whitepaper for policy stakeholders	(Completed) Created from roundtable hosted with SYBO games and UNDP at the NYC Climate Summit in September 2024.
27	100,000 unique visitors to the website	(Completed) Play2Act launched an updated communication strategy which will help drive more visitors to the website. This is due to linking back to the website on each blog post we share on social channels. We will also track data on LinkedIn and other social channels from posts including likes / shares and who they were from (stakeholders). Taking this approach helps to gain views to the website, but ultimately we are aiming for engagement to the project and this can also be achieved through engagement with posts and PR. Dashboards created to showcase data will also live online such as the PlanetPlay live data dashboard and soon UNDP will launch a dashboard, both will drive awareness. PlanetPlay's GREAT x UNDP Play2Act dashboard has seen over 125k views with 35k gamers interested to 'do more'. The dashboards will link to GREAT, however the visibility and engagement with these online spaces will be even more valuable to the project than views to the GREAT website solely.

Table 5: Updated progress of KPIs in July 2025

4.9 Political and Policy Dissemination Strategy

Dissemination to policy makers is an important part of the project, to raise awareness of activities and engage this group in the process, and eventually the outcomes. The GREAT project is mindful of the necessity within the project to engage directly with political and policymakers. The project will determine these actions informed by consultation with stakeholders and with the engagement of our project advisor located within one of the UK partners Baroness Worthington. The following activities have taken place:

1. Meetings with experts and key influencers - to gain knowledge, insight and guidance and as ambassadors able to promote the project and make relevant connections.
2. Host roundtables on and offline with policy makers and those involved with policy data such as at NYC Climate Week (September 2024 and 2025) and also bring

policy makers to gaming events such as Nordic Game (May 2025), to undertake deeper discussions and produce policy papers. GREAT attended the Games Policy Summit, which took place during Nordic Game 2025 together with our sister projects. The event brought together European stakeholders as well as game studios to examine policy measures to boost games industry growth on the basis of culture, innovation and trade.

3. Host meetings and events in conjunction with policy makers such as at the EU Commission's offices in Brussels, and attract key games stakeholders. A games cluster event at Brussels with the EU took place on 17 June 2025.
4. Work with existing groups who we know have political agendas, such as Playing for the Planet, UKIE, Project Everyone, Drawdown, UNDP, COP etc.
5. Create white papers and or determine the profile of papers that are required in the policy space in order to create impact and knowledge transfer to the policy domain.
6. Create specific policy papers for this stakeholder group, to inform on the importance of gaming in policy making.

5. Exploitation Strategy, Plan and KERs

This section presents a first version of the Exploitation Plan for the GREAT project outputs. It also contains a first assessment of the potential Key Exploitable Results (KERs), and the ways and methods the consortium will use to enhance impact and sustainability. The Exploitation Plan has been reviewed and it will be updated throughout the project lifespan, to foster smooth and successful exploitation of the project results. The project exploitation strategy, supported by the EU booster experts have supported us to identify our exploitation and business plans (as shown in sections 6 and 7. This existing project plan from the beginning of the project defines a long-term strategy until the end of the project, to pursue the following objectives:

1. Explore and assess application areas to facilitate the exploitation of the GREAT project results.
2. Set the foundations for further opportunities to ensure the achievement of impact during and beyond project end.

The strategies of communication, dissemination and exploitation of results, although they are all discussed in this document, should however not be mixed up. While these strategies share many similarities, it is essential to emphasize their differences. Figure 7 has been obtained from [“Horizon Europe Quick guide and tools for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation”](#) guide, and clarifies the differences.

Figure 7. Taken from [Communication, dissemination and exploitation. Why they all matter and what the difference is.](#)

The exploitation strategy aims to target three main audiences:

1. Consortium members, regardless of whether they are commercial companies, academic institutions or associated partners.
2. European Commission services and independent reviewers.
3. External organizations (industry, academia, society) and projects, especially those with an interest in GREAT results, further explained in section 5.4.

The exploitation strategy and the continuous process involved will feed into the input of the following GREAT project deliverables:

- D1.2 – Research data management plan: Research data management plan for the project including personal data protection measures. It will affect the creation of datasets.
- D4.4 – Compilation of GREAT scientific outputs: A public document detailing the scientific outputs including conference, journals and other publications produced by the partners over the duration of the project. It will have an impact on the exploitation of research findings.
- D5.3 – Final Impact Assessment Report: Final evaluation and impact assessment based on the evidence collected during the whole project.
- D5.4 – Policy insight briefs: Targeted policy briefs on game-based society - policy engagement based on the learnings from the project.
- D6.3 – Business models: this deliverable examines the business models applied in the domain of the use of games to link citizens in dialogue with policy makers examining policy dilemmas related to the climate change crisis.
- D6.4 – Revised dissemination and exploitation plan: Revised dissemination and exploitation plan, with toolkit and resources.

- D6.5 – Sustainability strategy: Sustainability strategy for the post project phase.

5.1 Common understanding: Terminologies

To understand the GREAT exploitation approach, it is necessary to understand what exploitation is and specifically to define the significance of the results and highlight the different terminological distinctions. Here, we also include some definitions of dissemination and communication, in order to highlight their differences with exploitation.

- **Results:** “any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected”
- **Dissemination:** “public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means, including scientific publications in any medium”
- **Communication:** “strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communication about 1) the action, and 2) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange”
- **Exploitation:** “use of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardization activities”. According to the definition, exploitation refers to the use of the results of the project. The definition does not address purely commercial needs and opens the scope of the application of results to different levels and to different domains to encompass commercial, societal, political and academic exploitation.
- **Commercial exploitation** is concerned with taking the GREAT results to the market, whereas **non-commercial exploitation** is concerned with the effective use of knowledge, models, methodologies and standards.
- **Open Source:** “any program where the source code is made available for use or modification as users or other developers see fit”.
- **Open Access:** “Online access to research outputs provided free of charge to the end-user”.
- **Open Science:** “An approach to the scientific process based on open cooperative work, tools and diffusing knowledge”.
- **Target audience:** “It is a group of people to whom messages are addressed”.
- **Stakeholders:** can be defined as “people, groups or organisations having an active role because of their interest in the activities of the project, e.g., European Commission, Funding Agencies and others”.
- **Networks:** “list of contacts that, even if they do not have an active role in the project activities, can contribute to the wide communication and dissemination of activities.

Networks can be of different types”. They can be political, administrative, and union networks, for instance, linked to opinion leaders, media, and scientific networks.

- **End-users:** “A group of persons benefiting from activities’ results”.

5.2 Exploitation and its impact relating to GREAT’s objectives

In this section, we present the exploitation strategy specific to the GREAT project, its objectives, and the expected impact it aims to have, followed by the identified Key Exploitable Results (KERs). These KERs will be analyzed and their Unique Value Proposition identified along with the domains and outcomes produced by the KERs. The relevant target audiences are also identified. The formalization of roadmaps planning activities and the definition of clear messages in accordance with objectives and target groups are presented.

The GREAT project's main goal is to find a new form of engagement and dialogue between citizens and policy stakeholders through the use of games. In doing this, the project will demonstrate that games can have a positive impact on social engagement, by exploring the innovative potential of a game space within which citizens are willing to express their preferences and attitudes. Four overarching objectives (as stated in the GA) are shown below:

1. **Objective 1.** Establish ways in which games can be designed to provide a link between citizens and policymakers. In other words, to produce new knowledge on the role of the games industry and non-commercial creative practices in the EU to benefit society.
2. **Objective 2.** Understand the actual and potential impact that games can have on citizens' engagement in social issues and challenges, and on policy stakeholders' awareness of citizens' attitudes and preferences. In other words, provide evidence of the impact of games on European society by carrying out case studies which focus on how games impact on citizens' participation in European society
3. **Objective 3.** Provide practical guidance for games developers and policy stakeholders. In other words. To generate proposals for improving games in terms of positive impact on education, skillsets, responsible business models, employment chances, social cohesion and creativity.
4. **Objective 4.** Assess the benefits and risks to individuals and society of using games to promote engagement with societal challenges. In other words, to provide evidence of the impact of games on European society, including their cultural value and risks.

As explained in the GA, the project does not only focus on providing academic evidence, but **to achieve a real impact on the selected target user groups, including commercial organizations and policy stakeholders.** Hence, the expected impact is:

New knowledge

- **Impact 1.** As a result of the implemented case studies, the project will generate knowledge on the role of games contributing to society, and the methods that can be applied by the games industry to achieve this.
- **Impact 2.** The project will generate evidence of the innovative potential of games and play, with practical applications in real cases. It will also create a knowledge pool, based on the data obtained from planned case studies, which will be made available to society for academic, commercial and social use.

New opportunities for society

- **Impact 3.** It will also demonstrate how games can be used to create new types of interaction and discourse on urgent social issues, new insights into social dilemmas, and new models of citizen participation in governance.
- **Impact 4.** It will enhance citizens' ability to participate in policy discussions. The increase in participation in policy discussions will have a consequent positive impact on social cohesion, proportional to the success of the project impact strategy. On the contrary, it will allow politicians to have direct access to citizens' concerns, thus contributing to decision-making on environmental issues.
- **Impact 5.** It will enhance citizens' awareness about the climate change crisis, while contributing to achieving the Green Deal and the UN Sustainable Development goals.
- **Impact 6.** The project will promote new forms of cultural expression. The Game industry is deeply creative and it's a terrific tool to foster intercultural cooperation, while engaging citizens of any age.

New challenges for the Games industry

- **Impact 7.** It will open and create a window for the video games industry to engage with, and better understand the needs of citizens, and the implementation of sustainable policies that affect them.
- **Impact 8.** It will contribute to the creation of new and innovative business models, applicable not only to the video game industry, but also to other public sector stakeholders.
- **Impact 9.** GREAT project will increase the potential of the games industry to collect data which is valuable for new and socially beneficial purposes, including new analytics tools and ethical data management methodologies. This will also open, in this sense, a new and sustainable economic activity for games developers and providers.

New capabilities for the consortium

- **Impact 10.** It will also create a network of game studios, intermediaries, legislators, non-profit associations, universities and other institutions aware of the use of games as a priority communication channel with the public to feed into decision making.

Throughout the collaboration with associated partners this network will assume a global status, with a presence in four continents.

The overall GREAT project Unique Value Proposition could be described as the opportunity to take advantage of the innovative potential of games, and play, to enhance new types of interaction and discourse on urgent social issues, collecting new insights into social dilemmas, and promoting new models of citizen participation in governance. All 5 identified GREAT Key Exploitable Results have their own unique value proposition and are presented in section 5.5.

5.3 Adherence to Intellectual Property Rights

Effective exploitation of the KERs depends on, amongst other issues, the proper management of intellectual property, which should be part of the overall knowledge management in the project. GREAT project Partners will assess the possibility or necessity of protecting their results once these are generated. In due course, they will choose an appropriate form of protection of intellectual property. Standard forms of protection which will be considered include patents, trademarks, industrial designs, copyrights, trade secret, and confidentiality agreements. In the GREAT project, the following actions will be carried out to address issues related to intellectual property rights, these include:

- potentially protecting the pre-existing knowledge (background) of the project partners,
- an assessment of the results generated during the project,
- proposals for the optimal protection of IPR, and
- ownership and proper implementation of IPR protection measures.

The framework of the IPR management is set out within the Consortium Agreement, which stipulates the rules related to the following IP issues:

- identification of the background and the specific limitations and conditions for its implementation.
- ownership of the results.
- access rights to the background and the results.
- non-disclosure of the information.

The GREAT project partners have considered it good practice to consult before deciding whether to protect new results, in particular if the results are a joint outcome.

5.4 KERs for Exploitation

The exploitation of the KERs will focus on how to maximise their impact and value. This process will consist of the following:

1. **Identification:** The project team will identify the most promising results with potential applications or benefits beyond the project.
2. **Assessment:** The identified KERs will be assessed for their market potential, societal relevance, and alignment with industry needs or academic interests.

3. **Protection:** Intellectual property protection mechanisms such as patents, copyrights, or licenses could be applied to safeguard the KERs and ensure their ownership. We will define this in the project at later stages depending on the requirements of project partners.
4. **Knowledge Transfer:** In the scientific context, exploitation may involve sharing research findings through publications, conferences, and collaborations, thereby contributing to the advancement of knowledge within the field.
5. **Dissemination:** Disseminating information about the KERs through targeted online activities, and events to attract potential stakeholders, or collaborators.
6. **Collaboration:** Collaborative efforts with relevant stakeholders, such as partners, research institutions, or policy makers, to ensure the effective utilization of the KERs.

By defining clear objectives, target audiences, tools, activities, and methods, the exploitation plan ensures the project's outcomes are not just made accessible to scientists, researchers, authorities, policy makers, but to encourage long-term use of results after the project has ended. The coordination of exploitation activities aims to achieve maximum outreach and impact.

Dimensions of Exploitation

The GREAT project consortium will focus on four dimensions to exploitation. Those dimensions are strongly linked to the expected results, and the selected targeted groups. These dimensions are *Commercial Exploitation*, *Societal Exploitation*, *Political Exploitation*, and *Academic and Research Exploitation*. These dimensions have been identified for the different target groups in order to find interest in the partnership activities allowing the creation or adaptation of specific messages to their communication habits.

5.4.1 Commercial Exploitation

1. *Project Partner Organisations* (PlanetPlay and SGI):

- Directly integrate the GREAT project's technology into their existing products and services.
- License the technology to other companies in the gaming industry.
- Use the data and insights to inform games studios, platforms and other industries interested in the data.
- Offer consultancy services to other organizations looking to implement similar solutions.

2. *Industry Groups* (Employers' associations, Unions):

- Utilise the project's findings to advocate for sustainable working practices.
- Develop industry standards and best practices based on the project's research.
- Use data to inform negotiations and collective bargaining agreements.

3. *Project stakeholders* (e.g., Games Studios and Developers):

- Improve green game design and development processes based on the project's methodology.
- Increase player engagement and retention through data-driven insights.
- Access and leverage the project's platform for user research and feedback.

4. *Platform Holders* (e.g., Unity, Xbox, Meta):

- Integrate the GREAT project's technology into their platforms to enhance user experience.
- Collaborate on research and development initiatives to further advance the technology.
- Use the project's findings to inform platform policies and guidelines.

5.4.2 Societal Exploitation:

1. *Sectors of Interest* (e.g. NGOs, lobbying and other organisations):

- Civil Society: NGOs and charities can use the project's platform and data to raise awareness of social issues, promote positive behavior change, and engage with their target audiences.
- Lobbying organizations (e.g., Think Tanks): Utilize data and research findings to support their advocacy efforts and influence policy decisions.
- Other organizations (International, Multilateral): Organizations like the UN or WHO could use the platform to address global challenges, promote sustainable development goals, and facilitate international cooperation.

2. Exploiting Data for Climate Change:

- Analyse in-game behavior to understand players' attitudes towards climate change.
- Develop games and simulations to educate the public about climate change and its impacts.
- Use the platform to promote eco-friendly practices and encourage sustainable behavior.

5.4.3 Political Exploitation

1. *Political Parties*:

- Engage with voters and understand public opinion on key issues through in-game surveys and data analysis.
- Use the platform to test different campaign messages and strategies.
- Run targeted campaigns within games to reach specific demographics and hard to reach audiences.

2. *Campaigning organizations*:

- Mobilise supporters and raise awareness for their cause.
- Gather data on public opinion to inform campaign strategies and push policies.
- Use the platform to connect with potential partners and volunteers.

3. *Legislative bodies* (e.g., MoP):

- Gather evidence and data to inform policy debates and decision-making.
 - Use the platform to consult with the public on proposed legislation.
 - Simulate the impact of different policies on society.
4. *Governments* (national, regional, local):
- Improve public services and communication through the platform.
 - Use data to understand citizen needs and preferences.
 - Engage with citizens on policy issues and gather feedback.
5. *EU institutions*:
- Promote European values and initiatives through the platform.
 - Facilitate cross-border collaboration and knowledge sharing.
 - Use data to inform EU policies and programs.

5.4.4 Academic and Research Exploitation

1. *Academic Partners*:
- Conduct further research based on the project's methodology and data.
 - Create papers and articles based on the project's outputs and build on existing research and knowledge.
 - Develop new teaching materials and courses using the project's findings.
 - Collaborate on future research projects in related fields.
2. *Associated Projects* (e.g., *EU Games Cluster*):
- Share knowledge and best practices with other projects in the gaming industry.
 - Leverage the project's results to strengthen the European game development sector.
3. *Research Networks*:
- Disseminate the project's findings to a wider research community.
 - Foster collaboration and knowledge exchange among researchers.
4. *Researchers* (*PhD candidates*):
- Use the project's data and methodology for their research projects.
 - Contribute to the development and refinement of the technology.
 - Publish research papers and present findings at academic conferences.

5.5 Progress on exploitation of KERs

In a collaborative exercise, in which all project partners were interviewed individually and jointly, the project team collected all of the expected results for the project to date. This is the first approximation that has been updated in Sections 6 and 7, with the support of the EU booster experts in the creation of the exploitation and business planning. The following table shows the result outputs, their description and the target audience they address, based on the four dimensions identified in section 5.4.

Output	Result Description	Dimension			
		Commercial	Societal	Political	Academic
Business models	Business models applicable in the domain of the use of games to link citizens in dialogue with policy makers examining policy dilemmas related to the climate change crisis, incorporating different value proposition. To help other companies to enhance its services.	✓		✓	✓
Business Models Ecosystem	A report and associated documentation detailing the GREAT business Model Ecosystem	✓		✓	✓
Whitepapers	A whitepaper on the use of games as a medium for education for democracy and development of skillsets in social engagement and participation. A whitepaper for policy stakeholders on the use of games to obtain policy insight.		✓	✓	✓
Policy Briefings	short insight documents from the project that are specifically targeted towards policy stakeholders to advise how the GREAT methodology can be useful for citizen - policy engagement			✓	
Data sets	The CSV files (or equivalent) of the data collected during the case studies	✓			✓
Online data sprint methodology	A suite of analytics methods for game activities	✓			✓
Corpus of case study documentation	The collected documentation of all of the research activities carried out in each case study (planning and reporting documents, working documents, transcripts, etc.)			✓	✓
Academic Papers (journals and conference proceedings)	Publications aimed at collecting the findings of the research activities carried out in the project. Journals, Conference proceedings...				✓
Other scientific outputs	Other results derived from the research activities carried out in the project. PhD candidates, Conference presentations, Posters				✓

Table 5a: A collection of expected results of the GREAT project

Network of stakeholder, including game industry, policy-makers, researchers	New connections for stakeholders involved in GREAT that may lead to further collaborations beyond GREAT	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Open Learning Resource	The Green Jobs and Green Roofs DiBL games as open learning resources		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
GREAT method instruments and documentation	Planning and reporting templates, guidance, data procedures (?),	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Games-based survey method	A games-based method and/or process for conducting large-scale surveys of citizens views on policy dilemmas	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Games-based focus group method	A games-based method and/or process for conducting focus groups		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Activity designs	A set of activities for use in the design of inquiries into citizens views on policy dilemmas, specifically (but not exclusively) games-based surveys and focus groups.		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
DiBL 2.0	An adapted and extended version of DiBL that addresses the feedback from researchers, partners, end-users and policy-makers across the GREAT project. It may include new templates, formats, open assets, data freely accessible	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
PlanetPlay services 'shared value' data - games	To access millions of gamers for no cost, have an agreement with games studios to provide access to their players in return for data and insights. Surveys, CTA,	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Table 5b: A collection of expected results of the GREAT project

For example, the business models, business models ecosystem outputs, network of stakeholder (including game industry, policy-makers, researchers) can potentially be exploited in the commercial, political and academic dimensions, whereas whitepapers and open learning resources can be exploited in the societal, political and academic dimensions. Policy briefs can be exploited in the political dimension. Both DiBL 2.0 and PlanetPlay services ‘shared value’ data – games can be commercially and politically exploited. From the list of 17 GREAT exploitable results as shown in Table 5a and 5b, we identified 5 results that are expected to deliver the largest and most meaningful impact of the GREAT project in relation to its overarching objectives as detailed in section 5.2. These are shown in Table 6 below, and further explained in the sub-sections 5.5.1, 5.5.2, 5.5.3, 5.5.4, and 5.5.5.

Note that a Key Exploitable Result (KER) is an identified interesting result, which has been selected and prioritized due to its high potential to be “exploited” – meaning to make use and derive benefits – downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education. The GREAT consortium has identified 5 results that fulfil the aforementioned prerequisites, based on their degree of innovation, exploitability and impact.

Key Exploitable Result	Dimension			
	Commercial	Societal	Political	Academic
Methodology for Games industry	✓			
Methodology for policymakers & organisations		✓	✓	
Datasets	✓			✓
Knowledge corpus		✓		✓
DIBL 2.0		✓	✓	✓

Table 6: Dimension addressed by GREAT project's Key Exploitable Results

(1) The methodology for Games industry, (2) Methodology for policymakers & organisations, (3) Datasets (further details provided in 5.5.3) and (4) Knowledge corpus **will be made publicly available on Zenodo**, whereas (5) DiBL 2.0 will not be made open source.

5.5.1 KER1: Methodology for the games industry

Description

A games-based method and process for

- 1) facilitating large-scale surveys to be carried out to collect gamer'/citizens' views, and
- 2) collection of in-depth insights, on policy dilemmas e.g., relating to sustainability or green games/communities.

Unique Value Proposition (UVP)

Using the methodology and tools made available by the project, companies in the sector will be able to open a new way of communicating with customers (via games), provide new services (surveys, information) and offer new products on the market, improving their productivity.

Tools/results linked to this KER

Business Models, Know-How, Games-based survey method, Activity designs, Templates, Surveys, networks.

5.5.2 KER2: Methodology for policymakers & organizations

Description

A games-based method and process for

- 1) facilitating large-scale surveys to be carried out to collect citizens views, and
- 2) collection of in-depth insights, on policy dilemmas e.g., the climate crisis.

Unique Value Proposition (UVP)

Using this methodology, different governmental organisations, associations and any other type of entity will have direct, reliable and quick access to the opinions of various population groups, which are usually not accessible to them.

Tools/results linked to this KER

Policy Insights, Whitepaper, Corpus of case study documentation, Games-based survey method, Activity designs, Open Learning Resource (educational game)

5.5.3 KER3: Datasets

Description

Collection of datasets from each case study of the project on citizens' views and insights into the climate crisis, which can provide understanding of potential affective and behavioural change in this domain.

Unique Value Proposition (UVP)

Access to the different datasets will allow access to big data related to the expectations of different population groups. It will facilitate analysis and decision making in various disciplines, primarily the climate crisis, environmental and sustainability issues. They can also be used in activities related to Artificial Intelligence or Data Science.

Tools/results linked to this KER

Data collection methodologies, analytic tools

Note that with datasets, the same principle from [D3.1](#) applies. This refers to data that is gathered during the GREAT project on climate area and is made publicly available. Portions of the data may be aggregated or individual fields removed to avoid identifying the results of individual games industry partners or the volume of their contribution to the dataset as a whole. Above will be made available on GitHub repository for ease-of-use, Zenodo platform, and/or the GREAT website depending on what is most appropriate for the specific output.

5.5.4 KER4: Knowledge Corpus

Description

Establish ways in which games can be designed to provide a link between citizens and policymakers. In other words, to produce new knowledge and understand the actual and potential impact that games can have on citizens' engagement in social issues and challenges, and on policy stakeholders' awareness of citizens' attitudes and preferences.

Unique Value Proposition (UVP)

Researchers in domains related to the project (citizen science, social sciences, democracy, participatory processes) will benefit from the results obtained for future research and future projects and thus be able to advance in the creation of knowledge.

Tools/results linked to this KER

Academic papers, conferences proceedings & events speeches, doctoral candidates

5.5.5 KER5: DIBL 2.0

Description

Provide a sustainable long-term commercial model where the methods and knowledge gathered in the project becomes available in a platform offer, so policymakers, NGOs and Higher education can get the benefits as a whole package.

Unique Value Proposition (UVP)

It provides a real-time space for informed conversations between policy-makers and citizens.

Tools/results linked to this KER

Go-To-Market for Ideal Customer Profile with offer, position and messaging for new audiences. These should be exploited in the medium and long term, mainly after the project ends. We have already exploited some results that should be highlighted to demonstrate that exploitation is occurring throughout the lifetime of the project.

5.5.6 Indicators to evaluate the degree of exploitation of KERs

The GREAT project partners have defined some initial indicators to evaluate the degree of exploitation of the project results. Depending on the development of the results, the impact of the project on the stakeholders, and the advice received from the Horizon Results Booster, these indicators could be fine-tuned in deliverable D6.4. Initially, the following indicators have been identified:

Academic dimension

- # of research institutions citing project results (new academic papers, conferences)
- # of new research projects originated from the results of GREAT

Policy Dimension

- # of policy stakeholders reached by Insight Briefings
- # of policy stakeholders reached by the 2 project whitepapers on the use of games as a medium for education for democracy and development of skillsets in social engagement and participation, and in the use of games to obtain policy insight
- # of public institutions adopt components of the GREAT methodology

Society Dimension

- # of people using GREAT developments (e.g., 300,000 people engaged in GREAT activities)
- # of other institutions adopting components of the GREAT methodology to address future societal challenges (NGOs, multilateral organizations, associations, unions)
- # of organisations adopting GREAT methodologies and technologies in expanding co-creation and citizen science activities (NGOs, multilateral organizations, associations, unions)

Commercial Dimension

- # of games companies engaging with future GREAT programmes and activities
- # of game studios adopting GREAT toolkit for applying the GREAT method to social applications of games
- # of companies using GREAT suite of analytic methods for game activities (through licenses or other legal schemes)
- # of companies, or start-ups, applying GREAT business models
- Measure of growth and sustainability of participant companies

5.5.7 Key communication and tools to increase the degree of exploitation

As project communication, dissemination and exploitation activities are somewhat inter-linked, which can collectively improve the visibility of the project. The time and resource investments in communication and dissemination events, will potentially increase the degree in which the project results are exploited and the impact reached. In this section, we summarise a number of key messages that can be communicated to different domains via different tools, in order to increase or maximise the degree of exploitation being reached, see Table 7.

Main messages	Dimension				Communication Tool
	Commercial	Societal	Political	Academic	
GREAT provides new ways for you to provide input to policy makers and implementers.	✓	✓	✓		Embedded activities in hit games. Press releases, blog posts on the website, social media
GREAT research provides new evidence and insight on the role that games can take in society				✓	Research publications, conferences, bibliographic listings on the GREAT website and books
GREAT provides a method and data analysis resources for implementing games leveraging game data for social purposes.	✓		✓	✓	Targeted contributions to industry websites (e.g. ISFE, EDPF) and leading bloggers. For data analytics: SOLAR, LACE network
GREAT reveals new opportunities for new applications of games, with guidance, resources, demonstrators and business models.	✓				GALA, blog posts on the GREAT website. Industry conferences (e.g. Games for Good, GDC, Gamescom)
The GREAT method creates opportunities for widening participation in your activities.		✓	✓		Networking by stakeholders (e.g. with UNESCO, UNECE, EC) and policy events (European Parliament events, User Centred Policy Design, Apolitical)
The GREAT method offers new ways to consult with citizens who do not participate in traditional media and democratic process, and to assess their preferences and attitudes.		✓	✓		Social media. Press releases and newsletters.
The GREAT method is a new way to obtain feedback on results of policy implementation.			✓	✓	Events with European Institutions, national Institutions (regional and local level). Social media. Press releases and newsletters.
GREAT insight reports can help you in formulating and responding to policy on the climate crisis.		✓	✓		Press releases, blog posts on the website, social media

Table 7. Key communication and tools to increase the degree of exploitation

5.5.8 Further support for exploitation

The exploitation of the GREAT project results are currently being enhanced with the support of the European Commission. Precisely, the GREAT project has engaged directly with the Horizon Results Booster service, which is a service / initiative from the European Commission that provides services to EU-funded projects to help navigate the complexities of dissemination and exploitation. The Horizon Booster's services encompass everything from dissemination and go-to-market strategies advancing results towards market readiness. The service is providing support to compliment and supplement the GREAT exploitation strategy. Further results of Booster support have been incorporated into Sections 6 and 7. Figure 7 below shows the different services provided by Horizon Results Booster in terms of communication, dissemination and exploitation.

Figure 7: Horizon Booster services (taken from <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>)

In February 2025, the project team had a meeting with the Booster experts relating to the go-to-market strategy for GREAT. At this point, the consortium should decide on 2 or 3 KERS for effective market exploitation and a 2 hrs Exploitation Pillars Training was provided by the EU expert to support this decision-making process and is a more general exploitation training to inform details relating to the exploitation journey of the project.

In the subsequent consortium meeting, partners collectively decided that out of the current 5 KERs - 1) Methodology for Games Industry, 2) Methodology for policy-makers and organisations, 3) Datasets, 4) Knowledge corpus, and 5) DiBL 2.0, we would choose two to go-to-market, namely DiBL 2.0 and Datasets. Our commercial game partners – PP and SGI suggested that they would plan to take the two KERs relating to the game platform or business strategy - DiBL (SGI) and Datasets (PP). Thereafter, SGI and PP each filled in some documents to provide further information on exploitation expectations, which were sent to the expert. Table 8 summarises the booster activities being undertaken with the EU booster experts to support the exploitation strategies of commercial partners SGI and PP. In these meetings, DIPF, UoB and UNIR were also often present to further support these activities, where and if possible.

Meeting Title & Date	Meeting Purpose	Attendees
Introductory Meeting (8.11.24)	Intro to Booster services, GREAT project & intended exploitation plan	Booster experts, PP, SGI, DIPF, UNIR, UoB

Introduction to Service Roadmap (29.11.24)	Including completion of feedback on Exploitation Readiness Assessment Tool	Booster experts, DIPF, UNIR, UoB
Introduction to GoToMarket Services (31.1.25)	To provide background information and to support the completion of GoToMarket documents	Booster experts, PP, SGI, DIPF
Exploitation Pillars Training (18.2.25)	To decide which KERs to exploit	Booster expert, PP, SGI, DIPF, UoB, UNIR
Unique Value Proposition – DiBL 2.0 (3.4.25)	To create a market definition canvas for expert feedback	Booster expert, SGI, DIPF, UoB
DiBL 2.0 Exploitation Strategy workshop (12.6.25)	To work on a detailed description of the exploitation strategy for DiBL 2.0, GoToMarket Characterisation Table, Lean Canvas, Exploitation Roadmap, Risk Assessment and Priority Map	Booster expert, SGI, DIPF, UoB
DiBL Business Planning workshop (2.7.25)	To work on details of the BOSAT (Business, Objectives, Strategy, Action, Timeline)	Booster expert, SGI, DIPF, UoB
DiBL Business Plan Implementation – Financial Plan (<i>to be planned for August</i>)	To work on marketing plan, pricing model, developing the solution based on customer needs	Booster expert, SGI, DIPF, UoB
Unique Value Proposition - Datasets (30.6.25)	To create a market definition canvas for expert feedback	Booster experts & PP only (due to meeting conflict with the consortium meeting)
Dataset Exploitation Strategy workshop (<i>to be planned for August</i>)	To work on a detailed description of the exploitation strategy for Datasets, GoToMarket Characterisation Table, Lean Canvas, Exploitation Roadmap, Risk Assessment and Priority Map	Booster expert, PP, DIPF, UoB
Dataset Business Planning workshop (<i>upcoming</i>)	To work on details of the BOSAT (Business, Objectives, Strategy, Action, Timeline)	Booster expert, PP, DIPF, UoB
Dataset Business Plan Implementation – Financial Plan (<i>upcoming</i>)	To work on marketing plan, pricing model, developing the solution based on customer needs	Booster expert, PP, DIPF, UoB

Table 8: Summary of booster activities being undertaken with the EU booster experts

6. Exploitation plan of DiBL 2.0 by SGI

The booster service has been used to identify the commercial exploitation potential of DiBL 2.0. This has been achieved through a combination of workshops, where 3 out of 4 have been held so far. The remaining workshop is scheduled for August 2025. This has resulted in updated models (shown below) that have laid the groundwork for a business plan that is currently in the first iteration. The Lean canvas below shows the key area of the DiBL 2.0 business mode.

The Lean Canvas		DiBL		
		25-04-2025		
		Iteration #1		
<p>PROBLEM Engage participants during facilitated events for real-time insights and active learning.</p> <p>OTHER ALTERNATIVES</p> <p>Status Quo * Powerpoints * Paper handsout * Facilitator exercises * LMS solutions</p> <p>Direct (Realtime audience tool) * Kahoot, Quizizz * MentiMeter, Wooclap * Bespoke solution</p>	<p>SOLUTION DiBL is a platform to create and deliver data active learning with real-time insights including formats like cases, scenarios, dilemmas, micro-sims, roleplays and workshops that are instantly available.</p> <p>KEY METRICS</p> <p>North star * # of participants * # of active creators * # of active DiBL cases</p>	<p>UNIQUE VALUE PROP Empower organisations to gather real-time insights through active participation and learning</p> <p>HI-LVL CONCEPT "Kahoot for dilemmas" "Powerpoint on steroids"</p>	<p>UNFAIR ADVANTAGE 20 years experiences building similar formats that we now productivize. Platform that is more flexible and powerful for advanced users compared to existing platforms.</p> <p>CHANNELS</p> <p>Direct sales & marketing Thought leader & SoME Customers using solution Direct sign-up own website</p>	<p>CUSTOMER SEGMENTS Organisations in EU with touch point where they facilitate presentations.</p> <p>* Higher education * NGOs / IGOs * Muncipalties * Corporations</p> <p>EARLY ADOPTERS Knowledge about facilitated learning, and existing alternative real-time audience interactions solutions in the markets, so they appreciate what we can deliver.</p>
<p>COST STRUCTURE Employee salaries (platform development + Sales) Marketing Hosting Admin cost</p>		<p>REVENUE STREAMS Yearly subscription Implementation services Content services</p>		
PRODUCT		MARKET		

Figure 8: Lean Canvas showing the key area of DiBL 2.0 business mode

Below we show two different key customer types: **Analyst and Educator**, that have different jobs that we should strive to solve better.

Figure 9: Value Proposition Canvas showing the customer segment: Analyst

Figure 10: Value Proposition Canvas showing the customer segment: Educator

The workshops also included additional tools and exercises like Go2Market exploitation roadmap and Characterisation table overview to create the skeleton, and additional risks assessment and BOSAT to identify gaps and weaknesses. This resulted in a first business plan draft, where the executive summary is shared below.

6.1 Business Plan - Executive Summary

DiBL is a spin-off with an experienced management team that worked in a related sector with bespoke projects. Through a small and agile team of 6-8 people they will create a professional and high-end offer in the real-time audience interaction segment through a PLG strategy.

- 2025: Soft-launch product, and establish core engine
- 2026: Launch product, and establish growth engine
- 2027: Scale product, and create and optimize fly wheel

Our projections show that the business will become profitable in year 3 with a total investment of €174.000, and as a SaaS business with a viral potential with good upsell options, and long customer relations can become an attractive EBIDTA of +40%.

There are well-entrenched companies in the space but they also rely on a self-service model largely that makes it difficult to add more advanced and complex features as it will jeopardize their core offering. On the other hand, they have a very strong viral loop, where a lot of customers are using the product providing free marketing that is difficult to compete with.

The strategy is to start in our small home market (Denmark), where we can provide a lot of value-added services that the bigger companies cannot, and then use those references and experiences to approach new markets. We can already see that in our home market customers strongly value features like domain knowledge, phone support, and personal onboarding. The challenge is that these won't scale in the long run but currently they provide a way to be close to customers to understand them, optimize the product and in reality, side-stepping direct competitors albeit in-direct competition is still very much in place.

We will most rely on PLG strategies for marketing and sales, where we have content marketing that leads into trials that we then close through self-service and low-touch outreach. We also approach customers with an LTV of +€50.000 through direct B2B sales. A key lead generator is also that both trial users and customers will typically expose the solution to 15-30 end-users that may be potential customers.

7. Exploitation plan of Datasets by PlanetPlay

The booster service has been used to identify the commercial exploitation potential of PlanetPlay's datasets. This has been achieved through a combination of workshops, where 2 out of 4 have been held so far. The remaining workshops are scheduled for July and August 2025. This has resulted in an updated value proposition:

'Our in-game sustainability tool helps marketing, communication and sustainability professionals who want to understand what their customers think and feel, by enabling them to reach "the hard to reach," and to get a high volume of responses'.

The exercise has enabled the team to better understand the role within an organisation, although the industry is agnostic. The target customer requirements is that they are working towards being a sustainable organisation and they require the datasets of PlanetPlay to help inform their strategies and communications. Figure 11 shows the updated Value Proposition Canvas, and Figure 12 shows the updated Market Definition Canvas.

The Value Proposition Canvas

Value Prop Statement: Our in-game sustainability tool helps marketing, communication and sustainability professionals who want to understand what their customers think and feel, by enabling them to reach "the hard to reach," and to get a high volume of completed responses (KPI).

Figure 11: Updated Value Proposition Canvas

MARKET DEFINITION CANVAS

Figure 12: Updated Market Definition Canvas

7.1 Business Plan – Executive Summary

PlanetPlay’s datasets have spun out of PlanetPlay’s not-for-profit organisation which has been focussed on enabling gamers to raise vital funds for on-the-ground green projects. PlanetPlay’s traditional model is around in-app purchase and the sale of games, viewing this as the perfect way to engage players to take an action while they buy their favourite games and gaming content. Datasets provide an important element to this existing work, to help inform games studios of what their players care about and enable them to be more strategic with their green activations.

However, the data can be used outside of the games industry for a variety of organisations who wish to be more strategic with their green strategies by better understanding certain demographics attitudes and sentiment towards the topic. Industries such as Utilities, Finance, Retail, Fashion and FMCG are examples of some of the types of sectors most interested in understanding their customers' sentiment on green products and services.

In terms of launch timings, see below:

- 2025: Soft-launch product with a few paying customers
- 2026: Launch product, and begin work on automation (applying for the EIC accelerator to support this next phase of development and commercialisation)
- 2027: Scale product, and create and optimize fly wheel

Our projections show that the business will become profitable in year 3. Funding beyond the GREAT project is being explored including the EIC Accelerator and other programs for follow-up funding to exploit this key result.

In comparison to other companies in this space, the USP of PlanetPlay is the existing games network PlanetPlay already works with who see the data as hugely valuable because they want to do more within the sustainability space. No other providers are working in-game in this way in terms of direct-to-player, direct in-game and discussing sustainability. The trust factor is also key as any new player would have to start from scratch to build relationships and trust, whereas PlanetPlay have established this already and strengthened this throughout the course of the project.

The strategy to exploit and commercialise will be to secure 2 to 3 partners towards the end of the project that would partner with PlanetPlay to test the datasets model, apply to their organisations and work with the PlanetPlay team to build an economic model which works for PlanetPlay, the partner and eventually the model for games studios to keep providing access to their players to gain these valuable insights. It is expected these first customers will be in Utilities and Financial Services. As we work with customers to review the value of the data and how we optimise, we can then discuss with games studios a royalty model in tandem.

We expect to gain customers through speaking and promoting at events, case studies with existing customers and sharing these on platforms such as LinkedIn and X, targeted media to specific audiences on LinkedIn and finally through word of mouth and referrals.

8. Potential collaboration with Federal Agency for Civic Education (bpb.de)

On 9.5.25, Simon Egenfeldt-Nielsen (SGI), Hendrik Drachsler and Jane Yau (DIPF) had a collaborative discussion with representatives from the Federal Agency for Civic Education (Bundeszentrale für politische Bildung / bpb) to explore opportunities for short-, medium-, and long-term collaboration, with a particular emphasis on synergies between civic education, game-based learning, and educational research. The participants discussed potential joint initiatives that could support the dissemination of the GREAT project's outcomes, such as:

- Integrating game-based approaches into civic education programs
- Co-developing public-facing dissemination activities, including workshops, events, or digital campaigns
- Exploring avenues for pilot implementation and long-term strategic partnerships involving educational stakeholders across Germany and Europe

The dialogue reflected strong mutual interest in leveraging interactive, research-driven tools to amplify civic engagement, particularly among young and traditionally underrepresented groups. This initial exchange opens the door to a promising collaboration pathway that aligns with both the GREAT project's mission and bpb's long-standing commitment to participatory and inclusive education.

While there was strong mutual interest, funding limitations were acknowledged as a key consideration for moving forward. All parties recognized the need to identify or secure appropriate financial frameworks—whether through EU programs, national calls, or cross-institutional partnerships—to support meaningful and sustained collaboration. The discussion laid valuable groundwork for future cooperation, with the shared understanding that innovative, participatory approaches to civic education must be matched with strategic resourcing in order to reach their full potential. The participants are currently exploring venues of funding.

9. Conclusions

This deliverable outlines the GREAT project strategic approach to communication, dissemination and exploitation as well as the mechanisms established to achieve maximum reach, impact and longevity for the project and outcomes of the project. As can be seen from the methodology and ability to leverage far reaching games, communication to a wider public audience is a key benefit of the project's communication abilities, and by end of 2024, the Play2Act case study in collaboration with the United Nations Development Program (UNDP) has reached over 130 million gamers worldwide. The deliverable also outlined communication in terms of how the WP6 leader and the consortium partners disseminate outputs and results. With a collective reach of 500,000 followers on LinkedIn, the project has the ability to reach a variety of stakeholders who are already associated with project partners and members. It also provides clear distinctions between communication, wide dissemination of the project and its outputs, dissemination targeted communication to those groups who may benefit directly from the work undertaken in the project and exploitation, how and by whom the outputs of the project will be used directly. It aims to establish the policies, procedures and processes in support of this objective. Further activities will be informed iteratively through stakeholder feedback and the activities undertaken as the project develops over the next months. This deliverable has been updated in month 30 as D6.4 with an up-to-date view on the progress of the KPIs, and the current exploitation activities being undertaken by SGI and PlanetPlay. All of our completed dissemination, communication and exploitation activities can also be found on www.greatproject.gg/blog, which shows the engagement of these activities by various consortium partners and members including DIPF, ZSI, FU, UoB, UNIR, SGI and PP as well as associate partners NWU and BNU.

Appendix 1: Games for Impact Toolkit

This toolkit was developed as part of GREAT's dissemination activities to offer practical, actionable guidance to developers, studios, and communicators seeking to align game-based experiences with climate and sustainability goals. It includes examples, recommendations, and design principles to help shape climate-positive narratives in gameplay. The toolkit is presented in a digital flipbook format and will be updated based on partner feedback and user engagement. **The toolkit is available [here](#).**

Appendix 2: Mentions of GREAT in external websites

1. Le Journal du Geek: [Les gamers sont de plus en plus écolos selon cette étude](#)
2. Digital Media Wire: [Almost 50% Of Players Make Greener Choices Playing Games Addressing Climate Change](#)
3. Radio Times: [Games with green messages can change your behaviour in real life](#)
4. Energy Live News: [Play on! Video games inspire greener habits](#)
5. GamesIndustry.biz: [Almost 50% of players make greener choices playing games addressing climate change](#)
6. TechPowerUp: [PlanetPlay & UN research reveals gamers' shift to greener habits](#)
7. PocketGamer.biz: [PlanetPlay reports 79% of players made eco-friendly changes after playing green themed games](#)
8. GamersGlobal: [UN-unterstützte Umfrage: Spiele können Umweltschutz fördern](#)
9. GameDeveloper: [PlanetPlay & UN research reveals gamers' shift to greener habits](#)
10. GamesBeat: [PlanetPlay's Play2Act poll finds 79% make positive change after playing green games](#)
11. UNDP: [Call for Game Studios to join Play2Act game poll](#)
12. UNDP Climate Promise: [Gamers adopt greener habits after playing green games](#)
13. UNRIC: [Play2Act units gamers for climate action](#)
14. Cassie Flynn, UNDP Global Director, shares on LinkedIn: [A new poll has revealed gaming can drive activity](#)
15. UNDP Western Europe: [Play2Act uniting gamers climate action in Western Europe](#)
16. GamesBeat: [PlanetPlay and the UN create Play2Act initiative to poll gamers about climate change](#)
17. Jerusalem Post: [UN collaborates with PlanetPlay to promote sustainable future, climate change through video games](#)
18. Angry Birds Friends: [Climate change and nature matters to everyone](#)
19. Gamesmarket.global: [Play2Act & UNDP](#)
20. Business Green: [Gaming for the planet: Can video games help drive climate action?](#)
21. Eneba hub: [PlanetPlay UN research reveals gamers shift to greener habits](#)
22. Tiga: [UNDP and PlanetPlay launch global gamer survey about the climate crisis](#)
23. Smileymovement: [Recent survey shares how gaming has connected many players to sustainability](#)

